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Determinants of Solar Energy Adoption Intention: A Meta-Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This meta-analysis investigates the determinants of individuals' intention to adopt solar energy by synthesizing findings from 16 empirical studies across diverse contexts. Using a random-effects model, pooled effect sizes were calculated for five commonly examined predictors: attitude, subjective norms (SN), perceived behavioral control (PBC), cost, and environmental concern (EC). The results show that attitude, SN, and PBC are significant and consistent predictors of adoption intention, underscoring the importance of positive evaluations, social influence, and perceived capability. By contrast, cost and EC were positively associated but did not demonstrate significant effects. These findings highlight that adoption intentions are primarily shaped by psychological and social drivers rather than purely economic or ecological considerations. The study offers theoretical support for the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and provides practical guidance for policymakers and practitioners seeking to promote solar adoption through strategies that strengthen attitudes, enhance self-efficacy, and leverage social influence.

Keywords: Solar energy, Adoption intention, Meta-analysis

1. Introduction

The global energy transition is increasingly centered on renewable energy sources as nations strive to meet climate change mitigation targets and reduce reliance on fossil fuels (IEA, 2020; Swain & Karimu, 2020). Among these, solar power has emerged as one of the most promising technologies due to its scalability, declining costs, and minimal environmental footprint (Abreu, Wingartz, & Hardy, 2019; Alsulami et al., 2024; Fathima MS, Batcha, & Alam, 2023; Liobikienė, Dagiliūtė, & Juknys, 2021). Governments and international organizations have implemented supportive policies, subsidies, and infrastructural investments to accelerate solar energy adoption (Assembly, 2015; IEA, 2020). Despite these advancements in technology and policy frameworks, the diffusion of solar energy at the household and individual levels remains uneven. Adoption rates vary considerably not only between countries but also across regions and communities within the same national context (Batool, Zhao, & Irfan, 2024; Jayaraman, Paramasivan, & Kiumarsi, 2017). Understanding the behavioral and psychological drivers behind individuals' intention to adopt solar energy has therefore become an essential area of scholarly and policy interest.

Over the past two decades, a substantial body of literature has examined factors influencing individuals' intention to adopt solar energy. These studies have drawn on diverse theoretical frameworks such as the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991; Asif et al., 2023), the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Bouaguel & Alsulimani, 2022; Davis, 1989), and the Value-Belief-Norm theory (VBN) (Stern et al., 1999), to identify determinants including behavioral, technological, and environmental. However, findings across studies remain fragmented and, at times, contradictory. For example, while some research emphasizes cost as the dominant barrier to adoption (Irfan et al., 2021), other studies highlight environmental concern or social influence as stronger predictors (Asif et al., 2023; Awais, Fatima, & Awan, 2022). Similarly, the strength of attitudes and perceived behavioral control has been shown to vary across cultural and regional contexts (Abreu et al., 2019; Fathima MS et al., 2023; Jabbour Al Maalouf et al., 2024). This inconsistency in empirical evidence creates challenges for developing unified theoretical insights and practical strategies to promote solar energy adoption.

While several narrative reviews have provided valuable discussions of the drivers of solar energy adoption (CR & John, 2024; Izam et al., 2022), no quantitative synthesis has yet identified which determinants consistently predict intention across different contexts. Existing evidence therefore remains scattered, limiting its ability to inform effective policies and strategies. A comprehensive meta-analysis is needed to consolidate findings across studies and clarify the relative importance of key predictors. Such an approach not only enhances theoretical understanding but also provides policymakers with stronger evidence to design targeted interventions. Moreover, it bridges the gap between fragmented empirical findings and the growing demand for renewable energy adoption strategies.

The objective of this study is to systematically synthesize empirical findings through meta-analysis to provide robust evidence on the determinants of individuals' intention to adopt solar energy. By integrating results from diverse contexts, this study aims to identify the most influential factors and assess their relative strength. To achieve this aim, the study is guided by the following research questions:

- What is the overall effect of commonly examined determinants on individuals' intention to adopt solar energy?
- Which determinant emerges as the strongest and most consistent predictor across studies?
- How do contextual moderators, such as country type (developed vs. developing) and study year, influence the strength of these relationships?

2. Literature review

2.1 Theoretical foundations

Research on solar energy adoption is often grounded in behavioral and technology acceptance theories. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) is one of the most widely applied frameworks, emphasizing the roles of attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control in shaping intention. In addition, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) highlights perceived usefulness and ease of use as central determinants of technology adoption (Bibi, Seher, & Aslam, 2025; Davis, 1989). Complementary perspectives such as the Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) theory extend this discussion by incorporating environmental values and moral obligations (Stern et al., 1999). Together, these frameworks provide a foundation for examining the psychological, social, economic, and environmental determinants of solar adoption intention. List of past studies conducted on solar energy adoption are presented in Table 2.

2.2 Attitude

Attitude reflects an individual's overall evaluation of solar energy adoption, shaped by beliefs about its benefits and drawbacks (Alam et al., 2021). A positive attitude linked to perceptions of cost savings, reliability, and environmental friendliness has consistently been associated with higher adoption intention (Bekti et al., 2021; Hasheem et al., 2022). Several studies report that attitude is often the strongest predictor in TPB-based models (Alam et al., 2021; Gajanayake et al., 2024).

2.3 Subjective norms (SN)

Subjective norms capture the perceived social pressure from family, friends, or society to adopt solar technology (Bibi et al., 2025; Lau et al., 2020). In collectivist societies, social influence often plays a particularly strong role, encouraging adoption through conformity and social approval (Jayaraman et al., 2017; Riaz & Awais, 2024). However, in more individualistic contexts, the effect of subjective norms tends to be weaker, reflecting cultural differences in decision-making (Gajanayake et al., 2024).

2.4 Perceived behavioral control (PBC)

PBC refers to individuals' perception of their ability to adopt solar energy, including financial capability, technical knowledge, and access to resources (Bekti et al., 2021). Studies consistently show that stronger perceptions of control enhance adoption intention (Alsulami et al., 2024; Liobikienė et al., 2021). For instance, homeowners who feel confident in their ability to manage installation processes or obtain financial support are more likely to intend adoption (Gajanayake et al., 2024).

2.5 Cost

Economic concerns remain one of the most prominent barriers to solar adoption. High upfront costs, limited access to subsidies, and uncertainty about long-term savings often discourage individuals from considering solar installations (Alam et al., 2021; Irfan et al., 2021). While declining technology costs and government incentives have reduced financial barriers in recent years, cost remains a critical determinant, especially in developing countries (Batoool et al., 2024).

2.6 Environmental concerns (EC)

Environmental concerns reflect individuals' awareness of ecological issues and their commitment to pro-environmental behavior (Jayaraman et al., 2017). Numerous studies indicate that stronger environmental concern is positively linked with solar adoption intention (Asif et al., 2023; Irfan et al., 2021). Individuals motivated by sustainability goals often view solar energy as a means of contributing to climate change mitigation and reducing carbon emissions (Fathima MS et al., 2023).

Overall, the literature suggests that psychological (attitude, PBC), social (SN), economic (cost), and environmental (EC) factors are central to explaining intention to adopt solar energy. However, the strength and direction of these effects vary across studies, highlighting the need for a

systematic synthesis. A meta-analytic approach provides an opportunity to integrate findings, resolve inconsistencies, and identify the most robust predictors of solar energy adoption intention. Further definition of each construct is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Definition of constructs.

Constructs	Definitions	Source
Attitude	An individual's overall judgment of a behavior as favorable or unfavorable, shaped by expected outcomes.	(Ajzen, 1991)
Subjective norms	It represents perceived social pressure from important others to perform or not perform a specific behavior.	(Ajzen, 1991)
Perceived behavioral control	An individual's perception of their ability to perform a behavior, shaped by resources, opportunities, and self-efficacy.	(Ajzen, 1991)
Cost	It describes individuals' perceptions of the financial barriers or economic feasibility of adopting a technology.	(Irfan et al., 2021)
Environmental concerns	The extent to which individuals are aware of environmental issues and motivated to act in responsible ways.	(Asif et al., 2023)
Solar energy usage intention	Refers to individuals' decision-making and actions toward installing or using solar technology.	(Alam et al., 2021)

2.7 Hypotheses development

Based on the reviewed literature and theoretical foundations, the following hypotheses are proposed, also shown in Figure 1:

- H1: Attitude positively predicts intention to adopt solar energy.
H2: Subjective norms positively predict intention to adopt solar energy.
H3: Perceived behavioral control positively predicts intention to adopt solar energy.
H4: Cost negatively predicts intention to adopt solar energy.
H5: Environmental concern positively predicts intention to adopt solar energy.

Figure 1: Proposed framework.

3. Methodology

3.1 Search strategy

A systematic literature search was conducted to identify empirical studies examining individuals' intention to adopt solar energy. Major academic databases, including Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar, were searched using combinations of keywords such as "solar energy adoption intention," "solar technology acceptance," "renewable energy behavioral intention," and "determinants of solar adoption." Boolean operators and truncations were applied to capture variations in terminology and maximize coverage. Peer-reviewed journal articles, and conference proceedings.

To ensure transparency and replicability, the review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (Moher et al., 2009). Studies were further screened for relevance through titles, abstracts, and full texts. This multi-stage process ensured that only methodologically rigorous and directly relevant studies were included in the final analysis, thereby enhancing the validity of the synthesis. In total, the search yielded a broad pool of studies from which eligible ones were systematically selected.

3.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Studies were included if they met the following criteria: (1) reported empirical, quantitative findings on individuals' intention to adopt or purchase solar energy technologies, (2) provided sufficient statistical information (e.g., correlation coefficients, regression weights, or other estimates convertible to effect sizes), and (3) were written in English and published in peer-reviewed journals. Studies were excluded if they focused solely on industrial or governmental adoption, relied only on qualitative methods, or failed to provide the necessary data to calculate standardized effect sizes.

3.3 Study selection process

The initial search produced a broad pool of potentially relevant studies. After removing duplicates, titles and abstracts were screened for relevance, and the full texts of the remaining studies were carefully reviewed against the inclusion criteria. This process resulted in a final set of 16 studies that were included in the meta-analysis. The study selection process is summarized in a PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 2), showing the number of records identified, screened, excluded, and retained.

Figure 2: PRISMA flow diagram.

3.4 Data extraction

From each eligible study, detailed information was extracted, including author names, year of publication, country, sample size, and theoretical framework. Key variables of interest attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, cost, and environmental concerns were identified based on their repeated appearance across studies. Reported statistics were standardized to Pearson's r to allow comparability across studies. Where a single

study reported multiple effect sizes for the same construct, effect sizes were averaged to avoid overweighting individual studies. Data extraction was carried out independently by two researchers, and discrepancies were resolved through discussion to ensure reliability.

3.5 Data analysis

Meta-analytic calculations were performed using a random-effects model, which accounts for between-study variability and assumes that the true effects may differ depending on study context (Borenstein et al., 2010). Reliability estimates were pooled to assess measurement consistency across constructs, while descriptive statistics summarized effect size distributions and sample characteristics. Correlation analyses were first conducted to examine overall associations between constructs, followed by formal meta-analytic tests of hypotheses.

Between-study heterogeneity was assessed using Cochran's Q and the I² statistic, with thresholds of 25%, 50%, and 75% interpreted as low, moderate, and high heterogeneity, respectively (Higgins et al., 2003). Publication bias and robustness were assessed using the Fail-Safe N (FSN), which estimates the number of additional studies with null results needed to reduce the overall effect to non-significance (Rosenthal, 1979). All analyses were performed using the metafor package in R (Team, 2016).

4. Results

4.1 Characteristics of included studies

The final set of 16 studies included in this meta-analysis represented a wide range of geographical contexts, theoretical foundations, and sample characteristics. While the majority of studies were grounded in the TPB. Sample sizes varied considerably, ranging from fewer than 200 participants to over 1,000 respondents, with a cumulative sample exceeding 5,000 individuals across all studies. The studies were drawn from both developed and developing countries, including China, Saudi Arabia, Australia, Lithuania, the United States, Malaysia, Pakistan, India, and others, providing a diverse comparative perspective. Key study characteristics are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of the studies included in meta-analysis.

Study	Sample	Country	Theory	Findings
(Alsulami et al., 2024)	415	KSA	TPB	A significant barrier to solar energy adoption in Saudi is lack of knowledge.
(Irfan et al., 2021)	355	China	TPB	Cost negatively while self-effectiveness, environmental concern, awareness and belief of solar energy positively impact.
(Liobikienė et al., 2021)	1005	Lithuania	TPB	The level of development and financial abilities influenced the most the intention to use.
(Asif et al., 2023)	847	China	TPB	Attitude, environmental knowledge, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, positively influence buying intention.
(Gajanayake et al., 2024)	179	Australia	VBN, TPB	Future orientation, values, attitude and perceived behavioral control play a significant role in installing solar.
(Alam et al., 2021)	382	Malaysia	TRA, TAM, TPB, DOI	Relative advantage, observability, subjective norm and awareness are strongest predictor of solar PV usage.
(Fathima MS et al., 2023)	351	India	TPB	Attitude, perceived behavioral control and energy concern are significant towards consumers purchase intention.
(Abreu et al., 2019)	400	USA	TPB	Social norms and attitudes have a significant impact on intentions.
(Jayaraman et al., 2017)	157	Malaysia	N/M	Intention to purchase solar system are mostly influenced friends, relatives or colleagues.
(Batoool et al., 2024)	620	India	TPB	Belief system, environmental concern, subjective norms positively while Cost and crime concern negatively influence.

Study	Sample	Country	Theory	Findings
(Bekti et al., 2021)	208	Indonesia	UTAUT2, TPB	Price value and attitude are key for solar energy adoption.
(Hasheem et al., 2022)	420	Pakistan	TPB	Consumer attitude has a positive and significant impact on purchase intention of solar PV products.
(Jabbour Al Maalouf et al., 2024)	450	Lebanon	TRA, TPB	A positive attitude toward solar energy strongly predicts purchase intention.
(Awais et al., 2022)	624	Pakistan	VBN, TPB	Personal and social norms have positive impact intention to use solar energy.
(Bouaguel & Alsulimani, 2022)	492	KSA	TAM	TAM constructs significantly impact the attitude toward the adoption of solar energy.
(Lau et al., 2020)	392	Malaysia	UTAUT	Social influence has the greatest impact on intention to install solar PV.

4.2 Descriptive statistics

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics of the included studies. Attitude was examined in 11 studies, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.06 to 0.99, and 91% of the reported associations were significant. Subjective norms were also tested in 11 studies, with effect sizes ranging from -0.04 to 0.71 , of which 82% were significant. Perceived behavioral control appeared in 8 studies, producing smaller effect sizes (0.02 to 0.42), with 75% of results reaching significance. Cost was reported in 4 studies, with a range between -0.001 and 0.44 , and 75% of associations were significant. Environmental concern, assessed in 5 studies, showed correlations between -0.08 and 0.68 , with 80% of findings significant. Sample sizes across studies varied widely, from 157 to 1,005 participants, with average samples for each predictor ranging between 379 and 488 respondents.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics.

Hypothesis	Relations	k	Correlations range		Correlations			Sample range		Cumulative sample	Average sample
			Lower	Upper	Sig	Non-sig	Sig (%)	Lower	Upper		
H1	ATT→INT	11	0.06	0.99	10	1	90.91%	179	1005	5149	468
H2	SN→INT	11	-0.041	0.705	9	2	81.82%	157	1005	5372	488
H3	PBC→INT	8	0.021	0.421	6	2	75.00%	179	1005	3787	473
H4	Cost→INT	4	-0.001	0.439	3	1	75.00%	157	620	1514	379
H5	EC→INT	5	-0.08	0.68	4	1	80.00%	157	847	2330	466

4.3 Reliability and validity of constructs

Pooled reliability estimates across included studies indicated that the constructs demonstrated high internal consistency. Attitude (average $\alpha = 0.844$), SN ($\alpha = 0.86$), PBC ($\alpha = 0.82$), cost ($\alpha = 0.88$), EC ($\alpha = 0.87$), and intention to adopt solar energy ($\alpha = 0.87$) were measured with acceptable to excellent consistency. These results confirm that the constructs were measured reliably across studies (see Table 4).

Table 4: Reliability and validity of constructs.

Constructs	Total Studies	Constructs Reliability			
		Average	Minimum	Maximum	Variance
Attitude	11	0.844	0.731	0.922	0.00297
Subjective norms	11	0.86	0.784	0.904	0.001908
Perceived behavioral control	8	0.82	0.607	0.94	0.010432

Constructs	Total Studies	Constructs Reliability			
		Average	Minimum	Maximum	Variance
Cost	4	0.88	0.864	0.897	0.000309
Environmental concerns	5	0.87	0.803	0.91	0.002095
Solar energy usage intention	11	0.87	0.687	0.966	0.005273

4.4 Pooled effect sizes

The meta-analysis revealed varying effects of the five determinants on intention to adopt solar energy (see Tables 5 and 6). Attitude (H1) showed the strongest positive relationship ($r = 0.37$, $p < .001$), followed by subjective norms (H2; $r = 0.28$, $p < .001$) and perceived behavioral control (H3; $r = 0.23$, $p < .001$), confirming their consistent predictive power. Cost (H4; $r = 0.18$, $p = .08$) and environmental concern (H5; $r = 0.25$, $p = .06$) were positive but nonsignificant, suggesting weaker and less consistent effects. Overall, attitude, subjective norms, and PBC emerged as reliable drivers of intention, while cost and environmental concern played a more limited role (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Constructs correlations.

4.5 Heterogeneity analysis

Tests for heterogeneity revealed substantial between-study variation. The I^2 values were consistently high, exceeding 85% for most relationships, indicating that observed differences in effect sizes could not be explained by sampling error alone. For example, heterogeneity was highest for attitude ($I^2 = 97.5\%$) and environmental concern ($I^2 = 97.3\%$), suggesting that contextual and methodological differences across studies influenced the strength of these relationships. This justified the application of a random-effects model.

Table 5: Correlation analysis.

Hypothesis	Relation	k	r (mean)	SD	r_+	r_z	95% CI LB	95% CI UB	FSN
H1	ATT→INT	11	0.3667	0.2881	0.331	0.4402	0.4175	0.4624	4360
H2	SN→INT	11	0.2795	0.2342	0.2616	0.2803	0.2555	0.3047	1856
H3	PBC→INT	8	0.2308	0.1469	0.2319	0.2349	0.2046	0.2648	573
H4	Cost→INT	4	0.1821	0.2074	0.2402	0.2524	0.2047	0.299	102
H5	EC→INT	5	0.2413	0.2941	0.3582	0.4024	0.3679	0.4359	498

4.6 Publication bias

Publication bias was assessed using the Fail-Safe N (FSN), which estimates the number of additional studies with null results required to reduce the observed effect to non-significance (Rosenthal, 1979). The FSN values indicated strong robustness for attitude (FSN = 4,360) and SN (FSN = 1,856), suggesting that these effects are unlikely to be overturned by unpublished or missing studies. For cost (FSN = 102) and environmental concern (FSN =

498), the FSN values were smaller, indicating that these results are more sensitive to potential publication bias, likely due to the relatively smaller number of studies reporting these variables.

Table 6: Meta-analysis.

Hypothesis	Relation	Estimate	SE	p value	95% CI LB	95% CI UB	Q	i ² (%)	Direction	Decision
H1	ATT→INT	0.37	0.0916	0.000	0.1869	0.5459	387.2926	97.51	Positive	Significant
H2	SN→INT	0.28	0.0702	0.000	0.1422	0.4175	217.5681	96.08	Positive	Significant
H3	PBC→INT	0.22	0.0491	0.000	0.1328	0.3254	44.3092	88.18	Positive	Significant
H4	Cost→INT	0.18	0.1066	0.087	-0.0239	0.394	63.7977	93.74	Positive	Not Significant
H5	EC→INT	0.24	0.1319	0.063	-0.0131	0.5039	184.0677	97.34	Positive	Not Significant

5. Discussion

The meta-analysis provides clear evidence regarding the determinants of individuals' intention to adopt solar energy. Attitude emerged as the strongest and most consistent predictor, confirming that individuals with favorable evaluations of solar technology such as its perceived benefits, reliability, and contribution to sustainability are more likely to express adoption intentions. This finding aligns with the Theory of Planned Behavior, which emphasizes the central role of personal evaluation in shaping behavioral intentions (Ajzen, 1991). SN were also found to significantly influence intention, indicating that social influence from peers, family, and community members meaningfully shapes decision-making. While the effect was weaker than that of attitude, this result suggests that adoption may partly depend on the perceived expectations of important others, consistent with previous findings in renewable energy contexts. PBC demonstrated a significant but smaller effect. Individuals who feel confident in their ability to manage the financial, technical, and logistical requirements of solar installation are more likely to form adoption intentions. This highlights the role of self-efficacy and resource availability in solar energy adoption decisions.

By contrast, cost perceptions showed a positive but nonsignificant relationship with intention. This suggests that while financial considerations are important at a practical level, they do not consistently translate into reduced adoption intentions across contexts. Policies such as subsidies or declining installation costs may explain this weaker and more variable relationship. Similarly, EC had a positive but nonsignificant effect, implying that while ecological values may motivate some individuals, they are not sufficient by themselves to drive adoption intention across diverse populations. Overall, the findings highlight that adoption intentions are most strongly shaped by psychological and social determinants (attitude, SN, PBC), while economic and environmental values play a less consistent role. This suggests that motivational, informational, and social drivers may outweigh purely financial or ecological considerations in determining adoption behavior.

5.1 Implications

For policymakers and practitioners, the strong influence of attitude highlights the need for awareness campaigns that emphasize the benefits, reliability, and performance of solar technologies. Promoting success stories of adopters may also strengthen positive perceptions. The significant effect of SN suggests that leveraging social influence through community-based initiatives, peer endorsements, or neighborhood demonstration projects could enhance adoption. Likewise, improving PBC through transparent information on installation procedures, financing mechanisms, and technical support can reduce uncertainty and increase confidence in adoption decisions. Although cost was not a consistent predictor, financial support measures such as subsidies, low-interest loans, and flexible payment schemes remain essential for lowering real barriers, particularly in developing contexts. Research further suggest that strategic communication, media engagement, and marketing efforts can play a critical role in shaping public perceptions and encouraging positive behavioral responses (Awan & Awais, 2023). Applying such strategies in the solar energy sector could reinforce adoption by addressing doubts, countering misinformation, and promoting a favorable social image of renewable technologies.

From a theoretical standpoint, the findings reinforce the robustness of the TPB in explaining renewable energy adoption. Attitude, SN, and PBC its core constructs, all emerged as significant predictors, providing strong evidence for its applicability in the solar energy domain. However, the nonsignificant results for cost and EC suggest that extending TPB with economic and ecological variables may not always improve predictive power, or that their influence may be conditional on specific contextual factors (e.g., policy incentives, cultural values). These results highlight the need for models that integrate psychological, social, and structural determinants of behavior, offering a more comprehensive understanding of solar adoption dynamics.

6. Conclusion

This meta-analysis synthesizes evidence on the determinants of individuals' intention to adopt solar energy, offering a clearer understanding of psychological, social, and contextual influences. The findings show that attitude, SN, and PBC are significant and consistent predictors of adoption intention. These results underscore the central role of personal evaluations, social influence, and perceived capability in shaping individuals' willingness to adopt solar energy. By contrast, cost and EC, while positively associated with intention, did not demonstrate significant effects,

suggesting that financial and ecological considerations may operate indirectly or in combination with other factors. Overall, adoption decisions are shaped more by motivational and social-psychological drivers than by economic or purely environmental values. This synthesis provides policymakers, practitioners, and researchers with actionable insights for designing interventions that strengthen positive attitudes, enhance perceived control, and leverage social influence to encourage wider adoption of solar technologies.

6.1 Limitations and future research

Despite its contributions, this meta-analysis has several limitations. First, the number of included studies was relatively small, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings across all cultural or geographic contexts. Second, the analysis focused on intention rather than actual adoption behavior, which can diverge due to practical barriers or situational factors. Third, only studies reporting sufficient statistical data and published in English were included, which may have led to the exclusion of relevant research from non-English or grey literature sources. Fourth, due to limited data, this study could not systematically examine contextual moderators such as policy incentives, socioeconomic status, or technological availability.

Future research should address these limitations by including a broader and more diverse set of studies, particularly from underrepresented regions. Longitudinal designs that track actual adoption behavior would strengthen evidence of causality and provide more practical insights. Scholars should also investigate the role of policy frameworks, subsidy programs, and cultural values in shaping adoption, as these factors may interact with psychological determinants. Finally, integrating emerging constructs such as pro-environmental identity, trust in technology providers, and perceived social responsibility could refine theoretical models and deepen understanding of the multifaceted drivers of solar energy adoption.

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